

APPLICATION OF FACTOR ANALYSIS TO SELECT OPTIMAL TEST DEPTHS FOR PROSPECTING AND EXPLORATION WELLS (USING THE EXAMPLE OF THE BUKHARA-KHIVA REGION)

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Geological objects, as a rule, are very complex and diverse, since their formation is usually due to the action of many different *factors (causes)*. Therefore, for a more complete specification of geological objects, they are usually characterized by a set of various features (*parameters*), and the measurement results of a set of these features are presented in the form of multidimensional random variables. In the exploration of complex geological objects, **factor analysis** allows a deeper understanding of the essence of the geological object, its genetic characteristics, which is extremely important when developing a strategy for *prospecting and exploration of mineral deposits*.

The results of 178 testing of exploratory wells drilled in the *Urtarabad and Sarytash fields* were taken as preliminary data for **factor analysis**. The analysis of the testing results was carried out in the context of assessing the optimality of the values of its intervals (geological-field task) and the possibility of using formal mathematical and statistical methods for processing actual data for these purposes (methodological task).

The object of research is carbonate **deposits of Jurassic age**. Reservoir rocks are pelitomorphic, fractured limestone, lump-clastic, algal-detrital and sulfitized. Types of reservoirs: *unevenly porous, fractured, slightly cavernous*.

During the analysis, only qualitative indicators of testing were taken into account. The following results were calculated at intervals every 10 m: - *hydrocarbons - oil, gas, condensate (HC); water; a mixture of water and hydrocarbons (hereinafter referred to as a mixture); drilling fluid filtrate and testing without inflow (dry)*.

For the eliminating the influence of the number of tests on the results of statistical processing, all data were converted to fractions of units. The generated test results are shown in Table 1

Analysis of a sample of the results of testing Upper Jurassic carbonates was carried out on the basis of factor analysis (principal component method).

The main goals of factor analysis are:

1) reduction of the number of data (data reduction);

2) determining the structure of correlation between data, i.e. classification. Accordingly, factor analysis is used either as a data reduction method or as a classification method.

For the initial data (see Table 1), load factors were calculated (Table 2), which can be interpreted as correlation coefficients between factors and data. Based on the results of testing productive horizons, a graph was constructed based on Table 1. (Figure 1)

Table 1
Testing results of Jurassic carbonates

Interval s, m	Sampling results amount. (th.) / proportion of units							Total amount of tests	
	HC	WATER		MIX		DRY			
0-10.	5	0.5	0	0	2	0.2	3	0.3	10
10-20.	5	0.55555556	0	0	1	0.111111	3	0.333333	9
20.-30.	4	0.36363636	2	0.18181818	2	0.181818	3	0.272727	11
30-40.	5	0.5	2	0.2	2	0.2	1	0.1	10
40-50.	6	0.42857143	2	0.14285714	3	0.214286	3	0.214286	14
50-60.	6	0.6	1	0.1	1	0.1	2	0.2	10
60-70.	4	0.44444444	2	0.22222222	1	0.111111	2	0.222222	9
70-80.	5	0.45454545	2	0.18181818	2	0.181818	2	0.181818	11
80-90.	5	0.45454545	2	0.18181818	2	0.181818	2	0.181818	11
90-100.	7	0.63636364	2	0.18181818	1	0.090909	1	0.090909	11
100-110.	3	0.5	1	0.16666667	1	0.166667	1	0.166667	6
110-120.	3	0.6	1	0.2	0	0	1	0.2	5
120-130.	3	0.5	1	0.16666667	0	0	2	0.333333	6
130-140.	2	0.33333333	2	0.33333333	0	0	2	0.333333	6
140-150.	1	0.33333333	1	0.33333333	0	0	1	0.333333	3

Table 2
Load factors

Testing results	FACTOR 1	FACTOR 2
HC	-	
	0,97264165	0,01086574
WATER	0,70811143	0,21150759
MIX		-
	0,15349558	0,64216077
DRY	0,61361303	0,03329669

Figure 1- Interval results of testing productive horizons

Factor 1 has high loadings for three testing results: “HC”, “water” and “dry”. Factor 2 has a high loading for the result - “mixture”. Based on this, factor 1 is identified as testing with a reliable result, and factor 2 as testing with the production of a hydrocarbon mixture. The dispersion plot of factor loadings (Fig. 2) clearly shows the separation of the test result “mixture” from “HC”, “dry” and “water”. “Mixture” is the influx of different fluids from the reservoir layers of the testing interval.

Figure 2-Dispersion diagram of factor loadings

This is explained by the fact that the testing interval may have included several layers with different fluids. Based on this, it is not possible to unambiguously determine the nature of saturation of reservoir layers in the testing interval. Consequently, testing with a result obtained in the form of a mixture of fluids should be considered apocryphal. The diagram separated “HC”

from “dry” and “water”. That is, the higher the “HC” result indicator, the less Dry” and “

water” and vice versa.

Figure 3-Diagram of factor values for testing intervals

The diagram of the values of factor 1 (Fig. 3) shows that with an increase in the testing interval, the probability of obtaining a “HC” increases. And after reaching a depth of 90-100 m it decreases. The increase in the probability of receiving “HC” with increasing interval is explained by the transition from the XV horizon to the XV-a horizon; the maximum number of hydrocarbon inflows occurs in the interval of 90-100 m.

The productive testing interval (up to 90-100 m) is characterized by the largest number of testings. Based on the maximum values of factor 1 up to 0.488 for “dry” and “water”, and the increase in the “HC” results, it can be assumed that the choice of an interval of up to 90-100 m or more for testing is the most optimal.

In general, this analysis allows us to conclude that the choice of testing intervals for Jurassic deposits in prospecting and exploration wells is quite correct for the selected part of the region.

Before analyzing the results of testing of prospecting and exploration wells, two tasks were set - geological-field and methodological. The methodological problem has been solved. Mathematical-statistical methods have good prospects in this area of research.

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